

PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT, UPBRINGING AND SOCIALIZATION

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Abstract. *From the first days of independence in our country, the implementation of reforms in the social, economic, cultural and spiritual sphere is setting important tasks for the education of the youth of our future great state of a mature generation, physically strong, competitive, with intellectual potential. This requires, first of all, the spiritual and moral education of the future generation in every possible way, to have knowledge, a broad outlook and faith in them. Because the future and prospects of our country depend in every possible way on the education of this generation. In this article, opinions and reflections on the development, upbringing and socialization of the individual will be covered.*

Keywords: *personality, upbringing, training, socialization, intellectual, biologic and social laws.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ЛИЧНОСТИ, ВОСПИТАНИЕ И СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИЯ

Аннотация. *С первых дней независимости в нашей стране осуществление реформ в социальной, экономической, культурной и духовной сфере ставит важные задачи по воспитанию молодежи нашего будущего великого государства зрелого поколения, физически крепких, конкурентоспособных, с интеллектуальный потенциал. Это требует, прежде всего, всемерного духовно-нравственного воспитания будущего поколения, наличия у него знаний, широкого кругозора и веры в них. Потому что от воспитания этого поколения всемерно зависит будущее и перспективы нашей страны. В этой статье будут освещены мнения и размышления о развитии, воспитании и социализации личности.*

Ключевые слова: *личность, воспитание, обучение, социализация, интеллектуальные, биологические и социальные закономерности.*

INTRODUCTION

Spiritual and moral education also has an important role in the formation of the personality worldview, and its effective organization contributes to the formation of spiritual and moral consciousness in the reader. Moral education is a pedagogical process aimed at the formation of moral consciousness, skills of moral activity, as well as moral culture in them, instilling in the minds of students the rules of behavior, criteria that are recognized by a particular society and need to be observed, and is considered one of the most important components of social education. The concept of personality is a comprehensive concept. Every person is Born This person. But its growth development is of great importance. From the moment a young child is one or two years old, upbringing begins for him. Training is also added to his side while he is seven or eight years old. Both are given equally throughout the years. Things he does not know are explained and, based on his interests, he is given a direction to a profession or profession. From this moment on, the child takes the first step towards his future. Now he begins to think about what behavior he has in the public and what developments he has. If a child is carried more inside people from a young age it will be easier for him to quickly enter into social contact and he will become a kata person.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concept of personality refers to a person and serves to represent a member of a society that is psychologically developed, distinguished from others by personal characteristics and behavior, has a certain behavior and worldview. For a person to be a person, he needs to develop psychically, feel like a holistic person, differ from others in his characteristics and qualities. In the national model of Personnel Training, a person is defined as the main subject and object of the personnel training system, the consumer of his services in the field of education and their implementation. Personality development. In order for a person to become a person as a social being, it takes the conditions of the social environment and upbringing. Under the influence of these, a person develops as a person and becomes a person. Development is a complex process that expresses the essence of quantitative and qualitative changes, manifested in the physiological and intellectual growth of the individual. Development essentially expresses the transition from simple to complex, from below to above, from Old qualities to new states, renewal, the emergence of a new, the disappearance of the old, the transition of a quantitative change to a qualitative change. The source of its development is the struggle between opposites.

The development of the child's personality is based on the philosophical doctrine that man is a social being. At the same time, man is also a living, biological being. Hence, the laws of the development of nature are also important in its development. Also, as an individual is assessed as a whole being, its development is influenced jointly by biological and social laws, which cannot be distinguished from each other. Because the activity, lifestyle of the individual, along with age, knowledge, life experience, is also influenced by other tragic circumstances, diseases. A person changes throughout his life. It matures both socially and psychically, in which the upbringing given to the child is purposeful, while it matures as a member of society and occupies a worthy place in the complex system of social relations. Because development goes under the influence of upbringing. In order to correctly see the qualities of a person and evaluate the impromptu, it is necessary to observe him in the process of various relationships. So, in order to correctly solve the task of personality development, it is necessary to know well the factors that affect its behavior, as well as personality traits. In order for upbringing to effectively affect the child, it is advisable to know and take into account the laws of growth and development. Thus, there is a bilateral connection between development and upbringing.

RESULTS

Up bringing is a practical pedagogical process aimed at the formation of certain physical, mental, moral, spiritual qualities in a person; the totality of measures taken in the way of ensuring that a person has the properties necessary for living in society. Upbringing is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures human humanity. Without upbringing, neither a separate person nor a society of people can exist. Because the values the existence of a person and society are transferred from one generation to another only due to upbringing. In the pedagogical literature, the term "upbringing" is used in broad and narrow meanings. In a broad sense, upbringing refers to the totality of all influences, activities, actions, aspirations that are aimed at forming a person's personality, ensuring his active participation in the production and social, cultural, educational life of society. In such an understanding, upbringing includes not only educational work carried out in family, school, children's and youth organizations, but also the entire social system, its leading ideas, literature, art, cinema, radio, television. Also, the concept of education in a broad sense includes education and obtaining information.

In a narrow sense, education refers to pedagogical activity aimed at the cultivation of the physical development, worldview, spiritual moral image, aesthetic taste of the individual. This is done by family and educational institutions, as well as public organizations. Education and obtaining information are not part of a narrow sense of Education. But any upbringing will exist only if it is closely related to education. Because in the process of education and obtaining information, it is accelerated that not only the knowledge of the individual increases, but also the moral and spiritual qualities decide. Socialization is a complex jargon that lasts a long time. Because in the process of development of any society, it develops a system of social and moral values, ideals, moral norms and rules, each child, having adopted the above rules, will be able to live in this studied society, to become its member. For this, society in one form or another purposefully affects the individual.

This effect is realized through education. On the second hand, the formation of the personality is influenced by various ideas, the social environment. People enter into a relationship with social norms and moral rules and study it. The jargon of socialization has internal contradictions. A socialized person must comply with the requirements of society, "enter" into it, resist negative aspects in the development of society, life circumstances that prevent the individual development of the individual. Taking into account the above features, in a social organization, a person is able to control and change consciously imposed biological restrictions, the model of his behavior, and control all higher psychological processes. Another personality trait is that he is able to change his will of Will and overcome obstacles in any situation.

DISCUSSION

This, social communication is characterized by the presence of certain information distributed through a wide audience, the purpose of which is to influence the behavior, feelings and emotions of people. In addition, there is only a presentation of information aimed at intellectual development public and expanding their worldview. Such a presentation is characterized by neutrality and maximum possible objectivity without elements of assessment. Some researchers understand social communication not only as a large-scale distribution of the message, but also as an individual exchange that takes place between two people. Its usual form is conversation. Although it corresponds to the definition of "social", it is often used in this sense when it comes to a group or a mass of people. Therefore, in this article we will use a common meaning. According to the type of audience, social communication is divided into specialized and public. The second category does not represent any originality and is ready to perceive any socially significant information. According to the source of the message, it can be both formal and informal: official statements of the authorities coincide with the first type, and, for example, rumors about the stars belong to the second. It can be both verbal and non-verbal through the delivery channel. Intention is purpose. A very important element, because the quality of perception depends on it. In the formation of a healthy personality, his attitude within the family depends on the upbringing received by his parents and the upbringing that he gives to his child. Personality and society are interconnected.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, society does not exist without individuals, they always complement each other. A person is a dynamic, proportionally stable integrity of the individual abilities of his consciousness and activity and the intellectual cultural moral and volitional characteristics of the

individual, expressed in individ. Personality is a dialectal unit of a common social and moral , special class, national and individual. In special historical cases, the personality acts like the integrity established by the social system. Personality as a social phenomenon is the reality of the individual and various topics of social communication. The social qualities of personality are manifested in its actions, relationships. According to these actions, to a certain extent, in the inner world of the individual, one can judge the spiritual and moral qualities of positive and negative qualities.

REFERENCES

1. Moskalenko V. V. Socialization of the individual: V. V. Moskalenko-Kiev, 2001.
2. Braagin S.V., Ignatovich I.V. The relationship between society and nature. 1999 year.
3. Yusupav E. Spiritual foundations of human maturation. - Tashkent, University, 1998.
4. Ismoilova, D., & Hudoyorov, D. THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN. *O 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O 'RTA MAXSUS*, 347.
5. Dilorom, I. "All Is Well, That Ends Well"-Stylistic Features and Shakespearean Language.
6. Dilorom, I. (2021). Communication Breakdown in the Heterogeneous Communication. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 1(6), 136-140.
7. Nurmatova, M. M., & Ismoilova, D. R. (2021). BUILDING THE STRATEGIC COMPETENCE IN THE HETEROGENEOUS COMMUNICATION. *ВЕСТНИК МАГИСТРАТУРЫ*, 65.
8. Ismoilova, D. (2021). SHAKESPEAREAN NEOLOGISMS AND THEIR PECULIARITIES. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(2).
9. Dilorom, I. (2021). Semantic-structural peculiarities of shakespearean neologisms. *Social Sciences, Humanities and Education Journal (SHE Journal)*, 2(2), 78-82.
10. Ismoilova, D. (2021). Pragmatic failure in the heterogeneous communication. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).
11. Ganieva, M. S. (2021). Socio-philosophical aspects of the study of the issue of gender and entrepreneurial woman in a new society. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(12), 441-445.
12. Ganieva, M. S. (2021). IN THE SOCIETY OF WOMEN-GIRLS INNOVATION-THE SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ESSENCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 947-951.
13. Ганиев, Б. С., & Ганиева, М. С. (2020). Семья как важный социальный фактор формирования предпринимательских навыков у молодежи (Опыт Узбекистана). In *Проблемы социальной психологии и социальной работы* (pp. 25-27).
14. ГАНИЕВ, Б., & Ганиева, М. С. (2019). Религиозно-исламские и духовные корни предпринимательской деятельности в Средней Азии. In *ИДЕАЛЫ И ЦЕННОСТИ ИСЛАМА В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ XXI ВЕКА* (pp. 332-335).